

5IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

**WP5 Dissemination and
education for HCPs,
pregnant and breastfeeding
women and general public**

D5.9 Interoperability and knowledge bank access description system which allows content from the knowledge databank to be adapted in national settings

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Document History

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Abstract

The aim of task 5.2 is to develop an EU centralised digital knowledge bank for healthcare professionals and pregnant women with up to date, reliable and evidence-based information on drug use before and during pregnancy, and on the risks of untreated disease (in English), by combining information from different sources and providing common knowledge. This report describes the interoperability and knowledge bank access. In addition it describes how the content from the knowledge bank can be adapted into national language settings.

As described in deliverable 5.8, during the process of writing the information pages, additional needs have been identified to improve efficiency. In addition, there was found to be a stronger desire than previously anticipated for the provision of translation of knowledge pages for countries that do not have a local knowledge bank. These updates are intended to ensure the knowledge bank is innovative and adequately addresses the needs of women and healthcare professionals throughout Europe.

Concerning the technical development of the MUMS website, the functionalities of the public website and the administration needed to upload an information page have been established. The website was successfully launched to the public at the General Assembly meeting in June 2024. The website is accessible and functioning in different browser settings and different devices. At launch, the website included 38 medicine information pages, five maternal condition pages and pages with general information in English.

To prove that the content from the knowledge bank can be adapted into national language settings, the multi-language functionality was developed and tested for two languages. For this purpose one language of a country with a TIS centre, but not knowledge bank (Italy) was selected and one language of a country without a TIS, nor a knowledge bank (Poland). The multi-language possibility has been proven.

Introduction

The aim of task 5.2 is to develop an EU centralised digital knowledge bank for healthcare professionals and pregnant women with up to date information on drug use before and during pregnancy, by combining information from different reliable and independent sources and providing common knowledge. The needs and expectations of healthcare professionals and pregnant women have been explored during the landscape analysis (see Deliverable 5.4 Report with landscape analysis). During the project, an additional need was established for the provision of translation into other European languages in addition to English of knowledge pages for countries that do not have a knowledge bank. In September 2024, an additional workshop has been held in which the future development of MUMS was discussed with stakeholders.

A description of the functionality of the knowledge bank and the standard operating procedure (SOP) for evidence retrieval and synthesis for the knowledge bank have been described in Deliverables 5.1 and 5.3 respectively. In Deliverable 5.8 the writing process has been described. After redesigning the writing process, the last years of the project the work focused on writing and finalizing the information pages on medicines and maternal medical conditions. In parallel, the technical functionalities of the knowledge bank have been developed and tested and the information texts have been entered. The website was launched for the public at the General Assembly meeting in June 2024. The website is accessible and functioning in different browser settings and using different devices. At the launch in June 2024, the website included 38 medicine information pages, five maternal condition pages and pages with general information in English. Since June 2024, the website has been optimized after receiving input from stakeholders. In addition, the website has been (partially) translated into Polish and Italian to prove multi-language functionality.

This document describes the current status of evidence retrieval, development of the knowledge bank and testing of the functionalities, the launch of the website and adaption into national language settings.

MUMS model update

Writing of information pages

During the writing process of the information pages, additional needs have been identified as described in Deliverable 5.8. While the previously proposed model was considered the ‘gold-standard’ approach to searching, reviewing, critically appraising, assimilating and summarising information about a medicine during pregnancy, the proposed process was very labour intensive, did not utilise existing resources developed by contributing partners and did not capitalise on work-sharing opportunities. Because of the enormous time investment required per page, this method proved unsustainable.

In response, a more efficient model for work sharing has been developed, where existing, trustworthy and independent sources of European and American Teratology information services are leveraged to compile summary pages, which will then be reviewed by an editorial board. Through this improvement in efficiency, we are now able to generate more knowledge pages in less time enabling a more complete and user friendly knowledge bank. It was identified that writing breastfeeding information pages takes relatively much time as experience in this field is lacking within the WP5.2 writing group. Additionally, there are existing sources with reliable freely available information in English (eLactantia and LactMed®) on this topic.

During the project, the following information pages were created:

- 38 Medicine information pages, with a MUMS summary intended for pregnant women and their health care providers and a detailed description for those interested in reading more detail on the scientific evidence.
- 5 Maternal condition pages, in a question and answer format, to provide more information on the disease and the impact on pregnancy.
- About Us page, including information on the writing process, authors and general information on MUMS.
- Disclaimer, including information on how information can and should be used and interpreted.
- 4 “In focus” pages, with information on the project, multi-language functionality and promotion of the E-learning package.

At the MUMS stakeholder workshop in Brussels (September 2024), the current content and best way forward for MUMS were discussed. A report has been created (see also deliverable 8.18). The most important conclusions are:

- There is a high need for an information source like MUMS in European countries currently lacking a TIS and knowledge bank.
- A minimum of 200 medicines is considered to be the desirable in order to be a valuable reference source for both patients and health care professionals. The added value of MUMS is the multi-language function, and that the content is available in local languages.
- It is important that every translation is verified by an independent (native) scientist to ensure reliability of the translations.
- It is important to create a roadmap on implementation and promotion for each country where the website will be implemented and promoted, as there are huge differences in how the health care system and information provision is set-up within the different countries.
- The list of drug names should be searchable in multiple languages. Currently, only the English name can be searched. However drug names may be written differently from country to country. Because of this, one may not find the drug in another language. This is to be incorporated in future developments.

Translation of information pages

As described in Deliverable 5.8, a need was established for the provision of translations of knowledge pages for countries that do not have a local knowledge bank. A pilot was started to establish this multi-language setting. In the pilot, one country with a TIS and one without was selected.

The initial idea was to use formal translation companies for the translations. Contacts have been made with several translation companies, and quotes were received. However, as there was no budget available to use a translation company, nor to pay for translation by experts, a different strategy was needed than originally anticipated in Deliverable 5.8.

The following two approaches have been piloted as part of the project:

(1) Countries who do have a TIS, but no knowledge bank – Example Italy

This pilot model was intended to explore translation of the website content in countries with a TIS centre and to explore the effectivity of AI-based translation.

As artificial intelligence (AI) language translation tools have quickly developed and increased in quality in the recent years, it was tested if a machine translation tool could be used. For the project the TransPerfect Tool was used. Through ENTIS, a teratology Information specialist in one of the Italian TIS centres had agreed to verify the accuracy and quality of this AI-translated texts.

(2) Countries who do not have a TIS and no knowledge bank – example Poland

This pilot model was intended to explore translation of the website content in countries without a TIS and to explore the effectivity of manual translation.

A few knowledge pages were manually translated by a Polish pharmacist . In absence of a local TIS or TIS representative in Poland, the translations were verified by another healthcare professional in the local country/local language to ensure accuracy and quality.

Note: Names of the contributing experts are not included into the report, but are available upon request.

Based on the pilot performed, the following was concluded for the translations:

- Manual translation is very time-consuming and therewith costly as a future option.
- (Manual) translation may result in slight changes in wording/nuances and content should be verified with its original English version.
- When making adjustments to the knowledge pages, one must be aware to implement these changes also in all available languages.
- Verification of correct translation is most effective when the person whom is verifying is an expert in the field of Teratology.
- Machine translation tools can be used, but need verification of the translations. Also one must be aware of the performance and validation of the machine translation tool. It was observed in the project that using Co-pilot, google translate or ChatGPT was less in performance, than the Transperfect tool. Using a machine translation tool, has a risk of incorrect translations and missing certain nuances in specific languages.

The most optimal route moving forward is considered to use a combination of a machine translation tool and expert verification. This route will also be used for the remainder of the pages to be translated into Polish.

For the future, an remaining issue is the liability of translation. The hosting (or governance) organization of the knowledge bank website remains liable for all content on the website. Making use of a translation company specialized in medical information might be a solution for this liability issue.

Development functional requirements

Public website (frond end) – Launch of website & Interoperability

Deliverable 5.1 described the functional requirements of the knowledge bank. All functional requirements for the home page are implemented technically. These include the functionalities for the search, recent knowledge updates, in focus, and maternal medical conditions. The website was made available to the public in June 2024: www.mums.eu. After the launch, input from different stakeholders attending presentations or the MUMS stakeholder workshop have been collected. Based on these suggestions, improvements have been made to the website to make it more intuitive and easy to use. For example, it was clarified what the website is intended for pregnant women and their health care providers . A view all button was made and the search function was improved.

All functional requirements for the information pages have been implemented technically. After clicking on the title, the visitor will be directed to the knowledge page. On top of the page is the MUMS summary. This is a summary of the information available in lay language intended for pregnant women and their health care providers. Below the summary is a detailed information section for those seeking more scientific details. Below the summary is an option to see the references used to create the page. At the bottom is a disclaimer and the update date. On the right of the page, related information pages are shown and the visitor can directly read these pages by clicking on the title. In Appendix 1, visuals of the website have been added.

Keywords of knowledge pages will be included as metatags in the code and the title of the knowledge page will be shown using a H1 tag on the website and will be part of the URL to increase the ranking on relevant keywords. In future, the search list can be further updated to include also ATC and SNOMED codes.

Using PiwikPro, website visits are monitored. This enables monitoring of the number of visitors and page views , as well as via which routing one visits the website (direct or via a link) and with what type of devices. The website is accessible and performing well via all browser types on desktop and mobile devices.

With these functionalities, and as the website is launched and now open to the public, we have secured the interoperability by enabling access to the data for pregnant women and their health care providers. Therewith this source of information can be used in daily practice.

An email contact address has been created: mums@lareb.nl.

Possible future functionalities may include, subscription to a RSS feed containing updates knowledge pages/news.

Public website (frond end) – Language and National settings

Functionalities for translation were developed. In June 2024, the website was launched with all information in English. In summer of 2024, translated content into Polish and Italian was added.

English is the basis of the website. All content is created in English as basis. A different language can be selected in several ways. Since the launch the option was present to select a language in the right top of each page. Options are to select English, Swedish, Dutch, German, French, Polish and Italian.

For European countries where a knowledge bank is existing, e.g. Sweden, the Netherlands, Germany and France, visitors are directed to those websites via a pop-up. This is because reliable information

in these local languages is already available. The information pages will not be translated into these languages.

For Italian and Polish, content has been gradually translated and added to the website. If you select these languages, you see the translated content, or English content where a translation is not yet available. On these pages, a notification is shown: “this page is not available for this language”.

As multi-language functionality is considered to be one of the key added values of MUMS, and based on feedback of stakeholders collected at meetings, the language functionality was further optimized. In future, it will be possible to select a language in the main screen, and also at individual information pages.

WP5.2 Writing team (Back end)

The website www.mums.eu has been embedded in the working environment of Lareb. At writing of this document, funding for MUMS from January 2025 onward has not been secured. To reduce costs and to guarantee that the website will remain accessible after the end of the ConcePTION project in 2025, the website was embedded into Lareb systems. The front end is not impacted by this, and therefore visitors remain to have the same experience as they would have in a stand-alone environment.

The back end is restricted and accessible via login by username and password. All functionalities to upload an information page on the website have been developed, tested and optimized. These include information pages overview, status, filter and selection for translation options, last changes from/to (date), keywords for search functionalities (e.g. drug name in other language), and links to other information pages.

Furthermore, there is the possibility of attaching documents to a knowledge page, such as, for example, the sources used. Comments can be put in the background, for example about discussion points between writer and reviewer about the content of the text.

An instruction manual has been written.

Branding

The name of the ConcePTION knowledge bank is ‘MUMS: Mothers Using Medicines Safely’.

As described in deliverable 5.8, preferences for the type of image in the logo and colors have been explored by using a poll. The logo has been developed in collaboration with the University of Stockholm (copy right agreed on).

At the bottom of the Home page acknowledgements and logos of participating parties for IMI are displayed. The website was verified and promoted by the IMI communication department.

The website has not yet been actively promoted outside the consortium. This promotion is included in future sustainability plans.

Sustainability

During the ConcePTION project, MUMS has been developed following well researched user needs and requirements. It is now a fully implemented web portal that is suitable for both desktop and mobile device access. After the ConcePTION project will end, it has illustrative content comprising of 38

medicines of high frequency use, developed through a formal and documented editorial and governance process.

After the ConcePTION project ends, Lareb has agreed to host and take over the governance and operation of MUMS in 2025. However, funding is required to widen the medicines coverage, translate the pages into multiple languages, to maintain and update the existing content and to promote the resource within target countries. Funding is also needed to continue hosting the website in 2026 and beyond.

A MUMS community is being set-up with people and organizations who want to stay or become involved in MUMS in the future. This community will contribute in finding funding, and will further collaborate on MUMS once future funding is secured. This includes TIS experts who want to be involved in writing or reviewing the pages, ENTIS as a network of Teratology Experts, and stakeholders from countries in which MUMS is of added value due to the lack of a local knowledge bank.

A sponsorship model is being pursued, through charitable agencies, to ensure permanent free accessibility for the general public and healthcare professionals. Industry sponsorship is deliberately not being pursued in order for MUMS to be demonstrably free from any concerns about a conflict of interest. Committing funding for a minimum of three years would be ideal, either through a single sponsor or an agreed co-sponsorship model. A bridging fund to enlarge the content as a first step is being pursued as well.

Maintenance requirements

Costs relating to the maintenance of the website will include web hosting fees, application support and updates of website functionalities in case of improvements.

Growth plans

The growth strategy may be guided by the priorities of sponsoring organisations. In general the aim is to extend the content to at least 200 medicines in English and other languages. The choice of drug may depend on the sponsor:

- a) most preferable; the most searched drugs in Europe (outcome of stakeholder workshop),
- b) the formulary of drugs used in particular disease areas nominated by the sponsor

Language translations (including quality assurance of these) and the promotion and implementation of the website in a specific country will be a significant portion of the annual budget.

Given that it will take time to accumulate content across all classes of medicines and therapeutic areas, it may be possible to prioritise inclusion of medicines information that is recognised to be in highest need for (most searched by women).

Whilst many of the medicines already , have been summarised by one or more TIS centres, the requirements of a sponsor may include coverage of medicines not yet reviewed and summarised by any TIS centre. In such cases, provided that funding exists for new content development, a TIS centre may be commissioned to create these pages. MUMS would only be able to establish its own content authoring capability, downstream, if the significant additional cost of new content creation is assured.

It should be noted that a key criteria for any future sponsor is that they cannot influence the scientific process nor medicine specific content of MUMS.

Funding and sponsorship

Funding is required for hosting, development, maintenance, to widen the medicines content coverage, translate the pages into multiple languages, to ensure the existing content remains up-to-date and clinically accurate, for management of the entire process (including liability insurance) and for promotion and implementation. Several national TIS centres have agreed to make their medicines information content available to MUMS to repackage and reuse, at no cost, so the required funding is to assimilate, streamline and quality check this content, and to translate, host and promote the resource within target countries.

Several presentations and communications have been given on MUMS since the launch in June 2024. In September 2024, a MUMS workshop has been held with multiple stakeholders (see also deliverable 8.18). As a follow-up, meetings have been scheduled with stakeholders and Lareb is setting up a MUMS network of future collaborators, supporters and stakeholders. The outcome from the validation has been positive. The need and desire for a platform like MUMS has been established at the workshop. Lareb will keep on hosting the website in 2025, so the platform will continue beyond the end of the project.

Regarding funding, a BMGF fund application was rejected. Also, interactions with EMA on MUMS related to the workshop did not lead to positive outcomes yet. Sponsorship is being explored and discussions are ongoing with WHO-UMC. Overall, funding beyond 2025 remains uncertain. Though several initiatives are ongoing and engagement on MUMS has increased last year, there is no clear outlook to a specific fund. Interactions with possible funders will be continued in 2025.

The project has laid a solid foundation for delivering reliable, multilingual drug information, though significant challenges remain. Key hurdles include demonstrating the tangible impact of MUMS to gain government buy-in, establishing trust and usability for the platform across diverse European contexts, and securing sustainable funding. However, ensuring the MUMS platform long-term viability will depend on overcoming these challenges and fostering stronger partnerships in 2025 and beyond.

APPENDIX 1. Pictures of MUMS website www.mums.eu

Main front page with top menu (for language selection) and the search option:

The screenshot shows the main front page of the MUMS website. At the top right, there is a language selection dropdown set to "English". Below this is a navigation menu with links for "Home", "About us", and "Disclaimer". The MUMS logo, featuring a blue water drop with a green figure inside, is on the top left, with the text "MUMS Mothers Using Medicines Safely" next to it. The main content area has a background image of hands holding a baby. Overlaid on this image is the text "MUMS: Information on the safety of medicines during pregnancy". Below this is a search bar with the placeholder text "Search here for medicines or maternal medical conditions". The search bar contains a search icon, the text "Search...", a "SEARCH" button, and a "VIEW ALL" button. Below the search bar is a section titled "Recent knowledge updates" which contains three cards. Each card has a title, a short paragraph of text, and a "Read more" link with a right-pointing arrow.

English ▾

Home About us Disclaimer

 MUMS
Mothers Using Medicines Safely

MUMS: Information on the safety of medicines during pregnancy

Search here for medicines or maternal medical conditions

Search... SEARCH

VIEW ALL

Recent knowledge updates

Multiple sclerosis

What are the effects of pregnancy on multiple sclerosis?...

[Read more >](#)

Epilepsy

What are the effects of pregnancy on epilepsy?...

[Read more >](#)

Valproate

Valproate (also known as sodium valproate or valproic acid, and various brand names) should be avoided in pregnancy wherever possible....

[Read more >](#)

Home page with In Focus section:

In Focus

Why MUMS

The majority of women will require medication use at some point during pregnancy. This may be short-term medication use, e.g. for a common pregnancy problem, or chronic medication use for medical conditions like asthma, epilepsy, depression or autoimmune conditions. Since the thalidomide disaster (late 1950- early1960), it has been known that medication use in pregnancy could harm the developing baby. As such, women who require the use of medicin...

[Read more >](#) May 2024

Multi-language

This prototype of MUMS is now in English, and first pages are available in Polish and Italian. More will follow in September 2024....

[Read more >](#)

Funding for MUMS

The ConcePTION Knowledge Bank, known as MUMS (Mothers Using Medicines Safely), is a publicly accessible and free-to-use bank of reliable and up-to-date informat...

[Read more >](#)

E-learning for HCP

The ConcePTION e-learning package is an introductory online training resource on teratology and medication use in pregnancy aimed at all healthcare professional...

[Read more >](#)

Home page with Maternal medical conditions:

Maternal medical conditions

Multiple sclerosis

What are the effects of pregnancy on multiple sclerosis?...

[Read more >](#)

Rheumatoid arthritis

What are the effects of pregnancy on rheumatoid arthritis?...

[Read more >](#)

Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE)

What are the effects of pregnancy on Systemic Lupus Erythematosus?...

[Read more >](#)

Epilepsy

What are the effects of pregnancy on epilepsy?...

[Read more >](#)

[VIEW ALL](#)

Example of search option and result:

The screenshot shows the MUMS website interface. At the top right, there is a language selection dropdown menu set to 'English'. Below it are navigation links for 'Home', 'About us', and 'Disclaimer'. The MUMS logo, 'Mothers Using Medicines Safely', is on the left. A breadcrumb trail reads 'HOME > SEARCH RESULT'. The main heading is 'Search results'. A search bar contains the text 'Cetirizine' and a 'SEARCH' button. Below the search bar, the results for 'Cetirizine' are displayed, including a brief summary: 'When needed, cetirizine can be used during pregnancy. There is a lot of experience with cetirizine during pregnancy. Based on current information, no increased risk of birth defects, miscarriage, preterm birth or any other pregnancy-related problems ...'

Language selection option (on top of every page):

The screenshot shows a language selection dropdown menu. The current selection is 'English' with an upward arrow. The dropdown list is open, showing the following options:

Home	Dutch	Nederlands
	Italian	Italiano
	Polish	Polski
	Swedish	Svenska
	German	Deutsch
	French	Français

And example of a knowledge page:

Cetirizine

🔍 Cetirizine

SEARCH

Pregnancy

When needed, cetirizine can be used during pregnancy. There is a lot of experience with cetirizine during pregnancy. Based on current information, no increased risk of birth defects, miscarriage, preterm birth or any other pregnancy-related problems have been reported.

Local allergy medicines such as eye drops or nasal spray, are often preferred when treating mild allergy symptoms. However, oral antihistamines such as cetirizine can be used, if local treatment is not sufficient.

Details

- Cetirizine is a second-generation non-sedative antihistamine medicine used to treat allergy and urticaria (hives).
- When treating mild allergy symptoms during pregnancy, local allergy medicines like eye drops or nasal spray are often recommended to limit systemic exposure. However, oral antihistamines can be used, if local treatment is not sufficient.
- There is extensive experience with the use of cetirizine during pregnancy.
 - No overall risk of major birth defects has been found in studies including more than 4000 pregnancies.
 - For outcomes other than birth defects, for example miscarriage, stillbirth, premature birth and being born small for gestational age, fewer studies are available. However, the available studies do not indicate any negative impact on the pregnancy or other pregnancy-related problems
- Limited research has been done on the possible long-term effects of use in pregnancy.
- Overall, the available evidence indicates that cetirizine can be used during pregnancy when needed.

References

Show ▼

DISCLAIMER: MUMS strives to provide accurate and up-to-date information, based on scientific evidence. The information provided may differ from the information in the patient leaflet and product information. We cannot guarantee that all information is actually up-to-date, correct and complete in all cases. This information is intended for pregnant women and does not replace medical care. Women are advised to contact their pharmacist, doctor or specialist if they have any questions about medications, health or treatments. See Disclaimer in top menu for more details.

Last updated: October 2024

Example of the used references (example Cetirizine)

References ^

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- Le Centre de Référence sur les Agents Tératogènes – CRAT. Cetirizine - Pregnancy. Jul 2021 [Accessed Feb 2024]. Available from: <https://www.lecrat.fr/3084/>
- Organisation of Teratology Information Specialists. MotherToBaby Fact Sheets: cetirizine. Jul 2022 [Accessed Dec 2023]. Available from: <https://mothertobaby.org/fact-sheets/cetirizine/>

Example of languages of countries where a knowledge bank is existing (Swedish, Deutsch, French and Dutch)

Notification

Er is geen vertaling beschikbaar in het Nederlands, omdat er een Nederlandse kennisbank is voor informatie over geneesmiddelgebruik rondom de zwangerschap: <https://www.lareb.nl/mvm-kennis/>

There are no translations available for this language because there is a local knowledge bank which can be found on <https://www.lareb.nl/mvm-kennis/>

CLOSE

Example of translated content (Italian) – home page

Italiano ▾

[Casa](#) [About us](#) [Disclaimer](#)

MUMS: Informazioni sulla sicurezza dei farmaci in gravidanza

Cerca qui i farmaci o le condizioni mediche materne

RICERCA

VISUALIZZA TUTTI

Aggiornamenti recenti sulle conoscenze

Sclerosi multipla

Quali sono gli effetti della gravidanza sulla sclerosi multipla?...

[Per saperne di più >](#)

Epilessia

Quali sono gli effetti della gravidanza sull'epilessia?...

[Per saperne di più >](#)

Valproato

Il valproato (noto anche come sodio valproato o acido valproico e vari nomi commerciali) deve essere evitato in gravidanza, ove possibile....

[Per saperne di più >](#)

Example of translated content (Italian) – knowledge page on Duloxetine

Duloxetina

RICERCA

Gravidanza

La duloxetina può essere usata dalla madre in gravidanza se necessario. Ci sono molte informazioni sulla duloxetina in gravidanza. Le evidenze disponibili non suggeriscono un aumento del rischio di difetti congeniti, aborto spontaneo o morte fetale. Se la duloxetina viene utilizzata nelle fasi successive della gravidanza, può aumentare il rischio di astinenza neonatale a breve termine o problemi respiratori nei neonati. La duloxetina può aumentare il rischio di sanguinamento materno alla nascita o alla nascita pretermine. Lei e Suo/a figlio/a potreste aver bisogno di un ulteriore monitoraggio durante e dopo la gravidanza.

La depressione non trattata durante la gravidanza può avere effetti avversi sulla madre e sul bambino, come un parto prematuro o un peso alla nascita troppo basso. L'interruzione improvvisa di un antidepressivo o il passaggio da un farmaco antidepressivo all'altro durante la gravidanza aumentano il rischio di ritorno della depressione.

Informazioni aggiuntive

- La duloxetina è un inibitore della ricaptazione della noradrenalina (SNRI) e della serotonina, utilizzato per trattare depressione, ansia e dolore neuropatico, tra le altre condizioni. Le decisioni sull'uso della duloxetina in gravidanza devono soppesare i benefici dell'uso della duloxetina rispetto ai rischi dell'esposizione alla duloxetina nei confronti del neonato.
- Le condizioni di salute mentale non trattate o sottotrattate possono avere conseguenze negative sulla madre e sul bambino:
 - Alcuni studi hanno riportato un aumento del rischio di parto pretermine, basso peso alla nascita e preeclampsia quando la depressione non viene trattata in gravidanza.
 - Le donne con depressione o ansia non trattata sono a maggior rischio di sviluppare depressione postnatale che può influire sul legame, sullo sviluppo emotivo e può avere implicazioni a lungo termine per il bambino.
 - La depressione non trattata può portare a una cura di sé e a un'alimentazione subottimali
- È importante che le condizioni di salute mentale siano adeguatamente trattate in gravidanza. L'uso della duloxetina in gravidanza può essere utile per mantenere in equilibrio la madre durante e dopo la gravidanza ed evitare alcuni degli effetti negativi della depressione o dell'ansia non trattata o sottotrattata.
- Esistono molte informazioni sull'uso della duloxetina in gravidanza, con dati su oltre 4.000 gravidanze esposte. La maggior parte delle informazioni attuali è correlata al suo utilizzo come trattamento per il disturbo depressivo e il disturbo d'ansia generalizzato.
- I dati sull'esposizione alla duloxetina in gravidanza non suggeriscono un aumento del rischio di difetti alla nascita, aborto spontaneo, morte fetale o compromissione della crescita fetale.
 - Vi sono alcune evidenze che suggeriscono che la duloxetina può aumentare il rischio di parto pretermine, tuttavia non è chiaro se ciò sia dovuto al farmaco stesso o alla condizione che viene utilizzata per il trattamento.
- Alcuni studi hanno osservato un aumento del rischio di emorragia post-partum quando la duloxetina viene utilizzata nel terzo trimestre. Ciò può essere correlato all'effetto della duloxetina sulle piastrine.
- L'uso di SNRI come la duloxetina nella tarda gravidanza è stato collegato a sintomi di astinenza neonatale, scarso adattamento neonatale e aumento del rischio di ipertensione polmonare persistente del neonato (PPHN). La PPHN si verifica quando la circolazione del neonato non si adatta alla vita al di fuori dell'utero dopo la nascita, con conseguenti difficoltà respiratorie. Il livello di rischio non è chiaro a causa della mancanza di prove di alta qualità in quest'area. Il rischio assoluto di PPHN è probabilmente basso.
- Alcune fonti suggeriscono che i bambini esposti a duloxetina in gravidanza devono essere partoriti in un'unità con supporto neonatale e monitorati per gli effetti avversi dopo la nascita come problemi respiratori, cianosi, difficoltà di alimentazione e ipoglicemia.
- Attualmente non vi sono evidenze chiare che la duloxetina debba essere evitata in gravidanza. La duloxetina può essere usata dalla madre in gravidanza se necessario.

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Example of the website via a mobile:

